

D4.1

Deployment of PoDIUM architecture to the LLs and development of data collection tools

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building
trust and sustainability for CCAM

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
5G	5th Generation of mobile technology standards
AD	Autonomous Driving
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAN	Controller Area Network
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CV	Connected Vehicle
C-V2X	Cellular V2X
CVM	Connected Vehicle Manager
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DPA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DT	Digital Twin
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FPS	Frames Per Second
G5	European standard for vehicular communications based on the IEEE-1609. X and IEEE-802.11p standards
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHz	GigaHertz
GPS	Global Positioning System
HMI	Human Machine Interface
IP	Internet Protocol

ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
ITS-G5	European standard for vehicular communications based on the IEEE-1609. X and IEEE-802.11p standards
IVIM	Infrastructure-to-Vehicle Information Message
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LLs	Living Labs
MAPEM	Map Extended Message
MCM	Manoeuvre Coordination Message
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
NMEA	National Marine Electronics Association
OBU	On-Board Unit
O-D	Origin-Destination
PC5	5G reference point for direct communications between UEs
PCAP	Packet CAPture
RESTful	Representational State Transfer
RM	Risk Management
RSU	Roadside Unit
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SPU	Sensor Processing Unit
SQL	Structured Query Language
TCB	Trusted Computing Base
TMC	Traffic Management Centre/Control
UC1	Use Case 1
UC2	Use Case 2
UC3	Use Case 3
UC4	Use Case 4
UC5	Use Case 5
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything

VA	Video Analytics
VAM	VRU Awareness Message
VIMA	VRU-aware Intersection Movement Assistance
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WGS	World Geodetic System
WiFi	Wireless Fidelity
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

The main objective of PoDIUM is to demonstrate and validate the applicability and benefits of connected and cooperative automated mobility (CCAM) in real traffic conditions. To achieve this, the facilities of three well-equipped living labs in Germany, Italy and Spain will be used. A rich set of demanding CCAM use cases will be investigated to identify and assess all the connectivity and cooperation enablers and needs that will allow the proposed higher levels of automation.

The present document D4.1 “Deployment of PoDIUM architecture to the LLS and development of the data collection tools” has been developed by Task 4.1 “Planning and deployment of PoDIUM platform architecture and data collection tools development”. The main objective of this deliverable is to provide a plan for the deployment of the entire PoDIUM architecture, as well as the definition and development of the data collection for the validation of such architecture and the evaluation of the PoDIUM use cases and scenarios.

The deployment of the PoDIUM architecture and the logging described in this deliverable is essential for a correct integration and validation of the project systems, happening in Task 4.2 “German LL integration and UCs pre-evaluation testing”, Task 4.3 “Italian LL integration and UCs pre-evaluation testing” and Task 4.4 “Spanish LL integration and UCs pre-evaluation testing”. Following these steps, the systems will be ready for the final demonstrations and evaluation in Task 5.2 “UCs technical evaluation and LL demonstration activities” and Task 5.3 “Public acceptance and impact assessment”.

Moreover, this deliverable contains best practices and guidelines for the definition and implementation of proper logging mechanisms to ensure success in the validation and evaluation steps of any data-driven project in general and in particular of CCAM-based projects like PoDIUM.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project intro

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UC) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the PDI system.
- Advance data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards digital twins.
- New C-ITS messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The deliverable D4.1 aims to define the deployment plan for each PoDIUM Living Lab and implement the data collection tools to allow the integration, validation and evaluation of the project systems, use cases and scenarios. The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled

1.3. Intended audience

This deliverable is classified as “Public”, therefore, it will be uploaded on the PoDIUM website, where it will be available for all project partners and any interested readers, as stakeholders and experts involved in the development of CCAM systems. Nevertheless, the consortium members are the main intended audience of this document.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable is organized as follows:

- Section 2 describes the PoDIUM architecture deployment plan
- Section 3 describes the technical guidelines for data management
- Section 4 describes the data management specifications from PoDIUM Living Labs
- Section 5 provides conclusions to the document

D4.1 content depended on D5.1 “PoDIUM evaluation methodology” for the evaluation methodology and the KPIs and will serve as input for D4.2 “PoDIUM LLS integration and pre-evaluation testing report”, D5.2 “Technical evaluation and demonstration of the UCs” and D5.3 “Public acceptance and impact assessment report” for the validation and evaluation of the use cases and scenarios.

2. PoDIUM architecture deployment plan

This section describes the plans for the integration of the developed systems, the testing required for the validation of such systems prior to the execution of the use cases, and the deployment of the whole architecture, including software, communication technologies and hardware.

2.1. UC1: Cooperative Corridor Management in City of Ulm

The following diagram shows the plan for the integration, pre-evaluation testing and deployment phases for UC1.

2.1.1. Integration plan

The integration testing succeeds the component development and integration. Components integration and subsystem tests will take place in Q3-Q4 2024. This incorporates the hardware setup and software development for the CAVs (Connected and Automated Vehicles), VRUs (Vulnerable Road Users), SPU (Sensor Processing Unit) infrastructure, MEC (Multi-access Edge Computing), and multi-connectivity features. The MEC is already set up and operational. The integration of software components has been finished in July 2024. Currently, the combination of various system modules is validated with overall system tests during pre-evaluation.

Integration testing is expected to be completed by the end of September. Testing of the integration with the infrastructure sensors and CAVs will take place shortly after.

2.1.2. Pre-Evaluation plan

Work on test methodology and KPIs alignment has been started since Q1 2024 and will conclude mid-Q4 2024. The pre-evaluation plan includes the preparation of the test environment (5G network, MEC, CAV, and roadside infrastructure), which was completed on time. All subsystems are expected to be tested and optimized in September-October 2024, so the functional tests can be completed until mid-November 2024. Starting August 2024, the overall use case will be tested, optimized, and validated. This work is expected to be finished until Q2 2025, which will also include the non-functional tests, after which the results will be analysed and reported.

2.1.3. Deployment plan and deviations

According to deployment planning (see Figure 1), these are the milestones for the different services and equipment:

- MEC: May 2024
- 5G network: July 2024
- SPUs: July 2024
- V2X communication: August 2024
- 60GHz-WiFi: September 2024
- Digital Twin: September 2024
- ITS-G5 RoadSide Unit (RSU): October 2024
- mmWave: October 2024
- Scheduler: October 2024
- CAV: October 2024
- Cooperative Planner: November 2024
- VRU app: November 2024

During integration testing, occasional issues with compute performance and connectivity issues may occur. However, the proposed timeline is viable to be completed on time.

2.2. UC2: PDI for User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs

The following diagram shows the plan for the integration, pre-evaluation testing and deployment phases for UC2.

Figure 2: UC2 integration, pre-evaluation testing and deployment plan

2.2.1. Integration plan

The integration plan among all components consists of different phases, which are planned in UC2 as follows:

- Components integration of the different components that is sequentially performed depending on the advance of different developments, their interfaces and APIs required in UC2. The integration phase began at the beginning of 2024, and it's planned to be finished by the end of October 2024.

With respect to MEC and Cloud deployments, it's expected to have them operational by September 2024, when the services will be deployed on both systems.

- Integration testing to verify that combined components and interfaces work as expected. First integration tests between IDIADA and ETRA services were conducted in May 2024, and they are planned to be finished by November 2024 by testing the integration between the Traffic Management and the Emergency Vehicles Management developments. Integration tests including the RSU and AI cameras installed on the street are planned by the end of October.

The preparation of the MILLA CAV for the integration with other components has been delayed as it was necessary to work further on the development of autonomous functions and route safety analysis for ensuring the best performance of the vehicle for a safe operation. Nevertheless, the planification to have the CAVs ready for the beginning of 2025 is not affected.

- Test methodology and KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) alignment, to align the planning for integration testing (data logging storage) with the KPIs previously set up and evaluate the success of the integration at, both platform and UC2 level. It has been carried out between March and July 2024.
- Documentation, that reflects all the integration system, has been carried out between April and July 2024.

2.2.2. Pre-Evaluation plan

The pre-evaluation plan consists of different stages whose planning in UC2 are the following:

- Test Environment Preparation, to develop a plan to ensure the success of the tests in UC2. It includes the preparation of the environment (RSU, Artificial Intelligence cameras, MEC and Cloud, 5G) but also of the vehicles (IDIADA CV and MILLA CAV). It is planned for Q4 2024.
- Tests with vehicles, to prepare them for operation, are scheduled according to the following plan:
 - First tests with IDIADA's CV, to prove that all components and communication systems are working properly, will be carried out from November 2024 to early 2025.
 - Before MILLA's CAV trials in Spain, preliminary trials will be carried out in France, both on open roads and in close circuit, in Q4 2024.
 - Then, once MILLA's CAV is ready and moved to Spain, safety and mapping trials will be carried out in January-February 2025, followed by connectivity field trials in March 2025, both to prepare the CAV for the final tests in April-May 2025.
- Functional Testing, to verify that the system performs all functions correctly as defined in the platform and UC2 requirements, is scheduled for March 2025.
- Non-Functional Testing, to assess performance, security, compatibility and reliability of systems, is scheduled for early April 2025.
- Results Analysis and Reporting, to finally analyse and document the test results to identify patterns, potential improvements and concerns in UC2, is scheduled between April and May 2025.

2.2.3. Deployment plan and deviations

According to deployment planning (see Figure 2), below are listed the milestones for the different services and equipment:

- Services that are already completely developed and will be deployed once the MEC and Cloud are ready: VRU App, Digital Twin, Environmental Perception Model, Collision Risk Estimator
- Connected Vehicle Manager (CVM): Development completed, including the interface with the RSU, and tested for 5G and C-V2X (Cellular V2X) at IDIADA premises. Once the RSU was provided, by the beginning of September, the software in the RSU will be installed allowing subsequent integration and validation of the CVM-RSU interface
- Traffic Management and Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning: September 2024
- Human Machine Interface (HMI) developed for the three scenarios: Completed in July 2024
- MEC: September 2024
- Cloud, both for deployment of services related to traffic management and services related to C-ITS Message Handling: October 2024
- 5G network: August-September 2024
- C-V2X: October 2024
- AI cameras, RSU and on-street cabinet: planned to be installed by October 2024
- Emergency corridor management, for corridor assignment, message sending and traffic light prioritization: November 2024

No critical deviations have been identified from the overall planning of the deployment, integration and testing phases have been identified that could affect the pre-evaluation tests planned for early 2025. The deployment of the MEC has been delayed because the decision on its final location has taken more time due to external factors. This has also affected the design and installation of the on-street equipment (cameras, cabinet, RSU), which as a result was delayed approximately by two months. No additional potential risks of major deviations are identified.

2.3. UC3: Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor

The following diagram shows the plan for the integration, pre-evaluation testing and deployment phases for UC3.

Figure 3: UC3 integration, pre-evaluation testing and deployment plan. The planned relocation of the UC has caused some deviations from the depicted original plan.

2.3.1. Integration plan

The original integration plan follows the components development. Components integration will take place in Q2-Q3 2024. This includes the development of interfaces and APIs. The MEC is expected to be set up and operational by July-August. Once ready, the Edge platform components can be deployed there. Integration testing will advance with the Edge components integration in the lab (remotely in the premises of each respective partner), then will validate their correct integration on the MEC. The Cloud will be integrated with the MEC at the latest by end of September. Integration testing is expected to be completed by the end of October. Testing of the integration with the RSUs and Cameras deployed on the highway will also take place around that time.

2.3.2. Pre-Evaluation plan

The test methodology and KPIs alignment has been developed since Q1-Q2 2024. The pre-evaluation plan includes the preparation of the test environment (5G network, highway roadside infrastructure) and the vehicles, in particular the MILLA’s CAV shuttle & IDIADA’s CV. Once deployed (expected in September-October 2024), the test environment will be tested and validated. To the extent feasible, tests will also take place with a CV (IDIADA’s) running on the highway, so that the whole system operational is ensured; this will take place late in 2024 or early 2025.

MILLA’s CAV needs first to complete and validate the upgrade of its AD function for 80km/h highway driving (SAE4). This will be first validated via closed circuit and open highway tests in France (2024), then via open road AD safety tests and connectivity tests in Spain (2025). Once validated, both the CV and the CAV vehicles will be used for functional and non-functional pre-evaluation tests on the highway.

2.3.3. Deployment plan and deviations

Deployment milestones (as per current plan):

- MEC: September 2024
- Cloud: September 2024 (including integration with the MEC)
- 5G network: September 2024
- RSUs & Traffic Cameras: October-November 2024.
- VRU app: September-October 2024

- Shuttle passenger app: September 2024

The deployments of the MEC, as well as of the RSUs and the Cameras have been delayed (due to the LL change from the AP7 to the C32 highways). The deployment schedule depends not just on our project partners but as well on external subcontractors. Any further delay may require postponing integration testing up to end of December. The overall timeline to complete pre-evaluation tests by end of May would still be feasible.

2.4. UC4: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance

The following diagram shows the plan for the integration, pre-evaluation testing and deployment phases for UC4.

Figure 4: UC4 integration, pre-evaluation testing and deployment plan

2.4.1. Integration plan

The integration started in January 2024 with the installation of the infrastructure and necessary hardware, either in the roadside and the CAV; also, edge required equipment started to be deployed. The integration tests were done during April 2024 and May between CAV internal components and OBU (On-Board Unit). In the meantime, the RSU was installed in the designated crosspoint. An update on the RSU and OBU is foreseen for mid November 2024, when PC5 short range interfaces will be installed, and edge software components will be available. During functional tests, VIMA (VRU-aware Intersection Movement Assistance) and DT (Digital Twin) will be prepared for further functional tests. Initial functional tests were done without DT and VIMA due to lack of integration between both components.

2.4.2. Pre-Evaluation plan

During June 2024 the tests were prepared together with the definition of the test methodology by all partners. In July the first systems were tested together to test functionality used in the UC4 scenarios. In this case the main risk being faced is the compliance with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) [6] which requires some additional technical requirements, due to the changes in the privacy regulation regarding the use of video streams taken from cameras located in public places. The GDPR compliance was obtained in July 2024 and the living lab was able to perform the programmed

functional tests. After the foreseen update, all the services base versions will be running and able to finish functionality tests.

Before performing non-functional tests, components will be prepared for release, fixing issues presented in the functional test phase, preparing also logging components and KPI measurements. On the part of software integrity components (TCB - Trusted Computing Base and SWint or Attestor) the first has been tested since early 2024 and will continue until the end of development of the attestor, where non-functional tests will take place together with all other components.

2.4.3. Deployment plan and deviations

RSUs were deployed at the kick-off of field installation; they were installed alongside a camera and a LIDAR and temporary with a G5 short range interface. The update in October will change this to PC5 interface. On the other hand, in-vehicle platform has finished deployment within the end of field installation programmed, with all its components, CAV components and OBU.

Regarding the sensor fusion platform, the components have been deployed and tested for functionality prior to the publication of this deliverable. The VRU has been deployed in a test terminal since April 2024 with basic functionality and will be ready for functional tests working together the VRU app and bicycle hardware parts as described in D3.2 [1]. VIMA and DT have been integrated to exchange messages and tested.

The latest deployment will be the SWint (attestor) that is currently under development and will be tested in parallel to other components.

2.5. UC5: Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel

The following diagram shows the plan for the integration, pre-evaluation testing and deployment phases for UC5.

Figure 5: UC5 integration, pre-evaluation testing and deployment plan

2.5.1. Integration plan

The CAV systems components have been tested and preliminary tests have been completed with the road operator as part of the integrated system tests. Other tests with the DT and remaining components are planned to conclude before the infrastructure installation.

2.5.2. Pre-Evaluation plan

Currently the logging facilities and procedures are being identified during Task 4.1 and the metrics are prepared to be calculated within these logs. Not all KPIs deal with the CCAM messages or timings, but with the reliability of the positioning, so CAVs have been testing the positioning techniques that do not require infrastructure. When all basic functionalities are tested in November 2024, other non-functional tests with the complete use case will start to prepare a second release with full functionality and expected results.

2.5.3. Deployment plan and deviations

Regarding the deployment of the components, RSUs are being deployed locally prior to be sent to the final tunnel premises. Local deployment is expected to finish by the end of November. CAV subsystems are already deployed in the vehicle at the time of publication of this deliverable.

The functional tests will take advantage of the closure for works of a tunnel longer than 500 m (closure that will take place during November 2024) and will perform ad hoc tests with CRF by setting up the V2X Locator instrumentation in temporary mode, i.e., without installing anything in the tunnel.

Infrastructure is ready with the necessary hardware to host DT, C-ITS and RM components. The software components will be ready in the phase period of the release preparation, since their development is still ongoing.

3. Technical guidelines for data management

Data is essential for all phases of a project. From the design phase, requirements elicitation, development, validation and evaluation, the data plays an important role to properly execute each phase and prepare the next ones. In fact, data required for the last steps of a project (e.g. evaluation) need to be defined or, at least, considered in the initial phases (design and requirements).

The following section propose guidelines for the data management especially focused on evaluation and validation data. They have been elicited from the knowledge and best practices extracted from the PoDIUM partners throughout past and current projects and, therefore, are focused on research and innovation contexts applying FAIR principles[2], following the Data Management Plan for PoDIUM project from D1.5 [3].

As a basis, the following data-related activities are proposed, to structure the guidelines and group them into meaningful categories:

- Data acquisition
- Data Transmission
- Data Pre-Processing
- Data Protection and Storage

3.1. Guidelines for Data Acquisition

The collection of data requires a proper definition of the WHY, WHAT, WHEN and HOW. This section describes the minimum requirements that should be considered before the actual acquisition of data.

3.1.1. Define clear data collection objectives and requirements

This initial phase is critical for every of the next stages where the data will pass through (transmission, quality checks, storage, evaluation, etc.). **Identifying a purpose for the data collection** is key to answer specific questions and hypothesis to address, as well as to determine how the data will be used in the decision-making process, which will lead to select the appropriate formats, sampling rates and other characteristics of the data.

In this introductory stage, the elicitation of **general logging data requirements about formats, units, ranges, resolution and location for technical (e.g. C-ITS messages) and non-technical data (e.g. user questionnaires) must be performed.**

Data quality requirements such as accuracy and precision, consistency, reliability or acceptable levels of missing or incomplete data should also be defined. They are sometimes not attended but their role is important to determine the sensors to be used and to meet the expectation for the analysis or evaluation of such data. An example is the vehicle positioning data (latitude and longitude), which requires centimetre-level accuracy for assessing certain manoeuvres of a vehicle (e.g. lane change), but more relaxed requirements in terms of accuracy are required for other type of manoeuvres (e.g. route change).

Legal and ethical requirements shall be taken into consideration. The data shall comply with the local, national, international and/or global data protection laws, depending on the applicability and the

impact area of the solution (more details can be found in Section 3.4.1). Aspects such as the consent, bias, discrimination, transparency, ownership, children’s data or revocation should be present in the requirements.

In PoDIUM, two main objectives are covered by the data logging, which are the “Validation of the systems” and the “Evaluation of the scenarios”. Specific logging has been defined to address each of the purposes, while the most restrictive/demanding requirements have been selected for both needs, to optimize the data acquisition process.

3.1.2. Establish sampling rates, data formats and relevant information

With a clear objective for the logging, identifying the relevant information to log is the next step. Depending on the final KPIs or validations to perform, the logging should be placed in specific locations to log specific bits of information. As an example, if the objective is to measure a latency KPI, it is required to log a minimum of a timestamp and an identifier in the source and the destination steps.

Following this guideline, **it is advisable to log a minimum set of common data for all logging.** As a general guideline, every logging line should include a measurement or metric, a time reference of when it has been collected, and an identifier.

A common mistake with the logging is to focus on the technical data required for the evaluation, without paying attention to other metadata which is used to properly select the right data among thousands of log entries of the same type. Good examples are the source of the information and the timestamp, since knowing when the log entry has been generated and from which component may not always be required to calculate a KPI, but they are useful to filter, process and/or compare only the relevant technical data for the validation/evaluation.

According to the Research Data Management (RDM) [4], mandatory for any Horizon Europe project, **the metadata shall:**

- **At least include the following fields: author(s), dataset description or abstract, date of dataset deposit or publication date, dataset deposit venue, dataset license and dataset embargo period (if any).**
- **Also include information about Horizon Europe or Euratom funding: grant project name, acronym and number. Ideally, the repository will have dedicated fields for this information. If not, you can include them in other appropriate fields, such as the abstract**

In PoDIUM, such mandatory metadata is expected to be included in the datasets during the uploading process to the warehouses (and not in the acquisition time), together with relevant information like the use case, the scenario and the device logging.

As the main data exchanged within the project are C-ITS messages, most of the use cases have identified relevant fields from each of the standardized C-ITS messages, as shown in Table 1. Such fields correspond to meaningful data required for the validation and evaluation of the PoDIUM systems and scenarios, which implies that other projects may require different fields.

Table 1: Proposed relevant information to log from each C-ITS messages

CAM (Cooperative Awareness Message) [13]	CPM (Collective Perception Message) [16]	DENM (Decentralized Environmental Notification Message) [14]	IVIM (Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message) [15]	MCM (Manoeuvre Coordination Message) [15]	VAM (VRU Awareness Message) [17]
Location (lat/lon)	Position of perceived objects (X,Y)	Detection Time	SpeedTarget	BlockedLane	Location (lat/lon)
Station ID	Direction of perceived objects	Station ID	RoadSegments	RoadSegments	Station ID
Speed	Speed of perceived objects	Event type (CauseCode)		TargetDistance	Speed
Longitudinal acceleration	Type of perceived objects	Sequence Number			Vehicle type
Vehicle type		Relevance Distance			
		Event Location (lat/lon),			
		Validity Duration			

However, this approach is not the only possibility when dealing with C-ITS messages, other alternatives are:

- Store the entire encoded C-ITS messages and post-process them to decode and get relevant information from them in a later stage (e.g. evaluation phase)
- Store the entire decoded C-ITS messages in form of JSON or XML formats, which improves human readability of the content.

Choosing the correct data characteristics (e.g., numerical, categorical, text, etc.) and defining the units of the data (especially for the numerical data) is fundamental to ease the next steps of the data management, including the quality checks, possible filtering of the information and the data storing. For example, the positioning data could be logged in multiple formats and reference systems, being Decimal degrees (WGS84), Degrees Minutes Seconds (WGS84) or UTM coordinates common formats. Sometimes, common logging formats from different systems are not easily obtained since they could depend on the sensors and measurement devices used (see next subsection 3.1.3). Another example are the “timestamps”, which could be expressed in multiple ways, even though a convention should be used for all logging data, being Unix time a very useful approach since it allows defining high granularity, such as microseconds or nanoseconds.

It is also advisable to **determine the acceptable range or categories for each variable**, since the analysis will require fewer preliminary steps to accommodate the data. For example, when comparing data from different vehicles, it is advisable to categorize all the vehicles of the same type under the same category (e.g. “passenger car”), instead of leaving some freedom in the category (e.g. “passengercar” or “passenger_car”) which could harden the comparison tasks.

Depending on the use case, the generated logging data volume could be huge. **Some requirements in terms of logging frequency and volume shall be defined if the transmission, processing and/or storage steps are forcing strict requirements** and cannot cope with such amount of data. Vehicle positioning and transmitted/received messages are example of usual heavy logging data.

3.1.3. Select appropriate sensors and measurement devices

The **selection of the appropriate sensor's types and location** for the data acquisition plays an important role in order to meet the data requirements and the scope of the logging.

The type of sensors varies depending on the logging environment (outdoor, indoor, software, hardware), the measurement requirements (physical, digital), the data requirements (range, accuracy, resolution) and other factors, being from temperature sensors, GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) devices to software application loggers.

The placement of the sensors and loggers needs to be selected based on the objectives of the data management, since in most of the cases the combination of different logged data is required to properly validate or evaluate the system. An example can be found for the evaluation of latency values, which require a direct comparison between metrics from the source and the destination points.

For PoDIUM, only software loggers are required for the validation of the systems and the evaluation of the scenarios. In few cases raw data from sensors is recorded. Since within the CCAM world most of this data is merged and encapsulated in C-ITS messages, these messages are the final logged metrics for analysis, as they meet the data requirements for minimum sampling rate and accuracy.

3.1.4. Implement calibration and time synchronization

It is mandatory to **check the calibration of the selected sensors and measurement devices** to obtain accurate metrics. Calibration is a periodic action, which shall be included in the maintenance tasks of the devices/equipment.

Since the data logged from different components and devices is usually compared or complemented to perform validation and evaluation tasks, **all logged data shall be synchronized in time**. Usually, the synchronization shall be performed in each of the loggers or components by using the same time reference, which could be internal clocks, public or private NTP servers, GNSS devices or other. If the same reference cannot be used (i.e. because not all components are connected to the Internet or use a GNSS device), then one must make sure that the different references are synched enough (e.g. in the order of few nanoseconds or microseconds) so the timestamps of the logging can be compared regardless the source of that logging data.

If that is not achievable, a time correction shall be applied at a later stage. This correction is feasible if the time differences between the references can be obtained.

3.2. Guidelines for Data Transmission

Once the logging data is collected, it could be stored internally in the same logger/component or transmitted into an external warehouse.

As mentioned in the previous sections, the logged data could be huge in certain scenarios. This forces to **select a transmission protocol that is efficient but, at the same time, powerful enough**. Many widely known solutions are available, such as HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol), FTP (File Transfer Protocol), TCP (Transmission Control Protocol) / UDP (User Datagram Protocol), WebSocket, Syslog or MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport). The following table compares these protocols:

Table 2: List of suitable protocols for logging data transmission

Protocol	Reliability	Speed	Overhead	Scalability	Ideal Use Case
HTTP	High	Medium	Medium	High	RESTful APIs, web-based logging
TCP	Very High	Medium	Medium	Good	Reliable, ordered log transmission
UDP	Low	Very High	Very Low	Very High	High-volume, real-time logging where some loss is acceptable
MQTT	Configurable	High	Low	Very High	IoT devices, distributed systems
WebSocket	High	High	Low	Good	Real-time web applications, live log streaming
Syslog	Configurable	High	Low	High	Network device logging, server logging
FTP	High	Medium	Medium	Medium	Periodic batch transfer of large log files
SSH	High	Medium	Medium	Good	Secure remote log collection, encrypted log file transfer

If the data is confidential, secure protocols like SSL/TLS (which can be applied on top of HTTP or MQTT), SSH or sFTP are essential for protecting logging data during transmission. These protocols encrypt the data, making it unreadable to potential interceptors. This is crucial for maintaining the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive information contained in logs, helping in complying with various data protection regulations (see Section 3.4.1).

In PoDIUM most of the platform services are deployed in the Cloud and in the MEC, being containerized or backbone applications, which generate logging data that is transmitted to the warehouses via HTTPs (HTTP over SSL/TLS) since the access requirements of the storages (e.g. Redmine and ZENODO) exposes a RESTful API. Such APIs also allow manual uploading of those logging data the transmission of which could not be automatized (e.g. some vehicle’s logging or from legacy systems).

3.3. Guidelines for Data Pre-Processing

It is advisable to perform operations over the logging data before being stored in the warehouses and/or being used for analysis. **Pre-processing of logging data is a crucial step that can significantly improve the efficiency, usability, and value of the logs.** Such processes are:

- Data validation**
 Relying on the loggers and the data acquisition process to follow all the data requirements is not advisable. **Ensuring that the logs follow the desired format, ranges and all other requirements defined in the design step** (see Section 3.1.2) can save time in later stages.
 Also, this process can detect duplications on the data (due to acquisition or transmission issues) and allows a way to handle errors to report, discard or resolve them.
- Data Cleansing**
Irrelevant or noise data should be filtered in this process. If the analysis of the data is automated, all data from pre-testing or integration should be removed to not alter the results. Duplications deletion and format corrections are advisable tasks within this processing.
- Data Normalization**
 As described in the Data Acquisition section, the data should contain normalized information in order to ease the analysis. For example, timestamps or location data should follow the same

format for all logging. If this is not the case from the data acquisition, a **pre-processing is required to guarantee that formats are consistent among the logging.**

- **Data Enrichment**

Sometimes, **the data captured needs additional contextual information or metadata to be completed** (e.g. related use case or scenario executed). Moreover, correlating data from multiple sources could also be required.

- **Data Categorization**

Categorize the data generated based on sensitivity is important to apply appropriate storage and security measures.

Co-funded research projects like PoDIUM have obligations with respect to data, including complying with data protection regulations (see Section 3.4.1) and the Research Data Management (RDM) [4] in the case of Horizon Europe programme. Openness, transparency and reproducibility are key aspects that the data generated within a project shall comply, following the FAIR principles [2].

Therefore, **the data generated should be classified as public, internal, confidential or highly confidential**, where:

- Public: Information that can be shared.
- Internal: Data for use within the project members.
- Confidential: Sensitive information with restricted access.
- Highly Confidential: Critical data requiring the strictest protection.

It is understood that not all data can be shared, since the confidentiality and privacy shall be respected, but processes like **anonymization** (e.g. video blurring to hide license plates and faces, id changes to avoid traceability, etc.) **can help converting private data to shareable pieces of information of great value** for other communities, researchers, etc.

- **Time Synchronization**

The **time synchronization** between the different logging data is a must if the time is critical for the analysis and/or validation. As described in the Data Acquisition section, if the synchronization is not performed at the loggers' level, it **can be done at a later stage such as in the pre-processing**. However, any correction of the time of the logs requires having information about the desynchronization between the different time references.

- **Data Compression**

At this stage, **data compression can also be applied to reduce transmission or storage requirements** (e.g. compressing files to ZIP or RAR formats). This compression can be loss-free (lossless), which reduces the size of data without losing any information or lossy, which reduces data size by eliminating some information, typically targeting data that is less noticeable or less critical.

In general terms, loss-free compression ensures data integrity (crucial for data logging in scenarios where every bit of information is important, such as Engine Control Unit (ECU) data, precise sensor

readings, safety-critical system logs and diagnostic information) but typically achieves lower compression ratios. Lossy compression can achieve higher compression ratios useful in automotive data logging for high-volume sensor data (e.g., camera feeds), audio recordings and non-critical telemetry data), saving storage space and transmission bandwidth, but at the cost of some data fidelity.

3.4. Guidelines for Data Protection and Storage

Depending on the infrastructure available and the objective, **the logging data can pass through multiple storages before reaching the final warehouse**. This is common when the logs cannot be automatically uploaded from the source (logger), either because the final warehouse is technically unreachable (there is no direct and automatic way to move the files there) or the format/content does not fit the requirements for the validation or evaluation, which will require temporary storage to pre-process the data before being stored in the targeted place.

3.4.1. Comply with data protection policies

When dealing with personal data, ensuring compliance with relevant data protection regulations is not only a legal requirement but also a best practice for data protection. This involves understanding the specific requirements of the applicable regulations and implementing measures to comply with them. In Europe the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [6] rules how the privacy of the personal data must be respected (more detail in the next section 3.4.1.1).

3.4.1.1. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The Regulation (EU) 2016/679 [6] is a comprehensive data privacy law implemented by the European Union in 2018, setting a new global standard for data protection and privacy rights. It applies to all organizations processing personal data of EU residents, regardless of the company's location. GDPR emphasizes key principles such as data minimization, purpose and storage limitation, requiring organizations to collect only necessary data and store it for no longer than required. It grants individuals significant rights over their personal data, including the right to access, rectify, erase, and port their data, as well as the right to object to certain processing activities. Organizations must implement robust security measures, conduct data protection impact assessments for high-risk processing activities, and report data breaches within 72 hours of discovery. GDPR mandates the appointment of Data Protection Officers for certain organizations and requires explicit consent for data processing in many cases. Non-compliance can result in severe penalties. A summary of the main principles is:

- **Scope:** Applies to all organizations processing personal data of EU residents, regardless of the company's location.
- **Consent:** Requires clear, affirmative consent for data collection and processing.
- **Data Subject Rights:** Grants individuals rights including access, rectification, erasure, and data portability.
- **Privacy by Design:** Mandates data protection measures be built into products and services from the earliest stages.
- **Data Protection Officers:** Requires appointment of DPOs for certain organizations.
- **Breach Notification:** Obliges reporting of data breaches within 72 hours.

- Penalties: Imposes significant fines for non-compliance, up to €20 million or 4% of global annual turnover.
- Accountability: Organizations must demonstrate compliance through documentation and impact assessments.
- Data Transfers: Restricts transfer of personal data outside the EU to countries with adequate protection levels.
- Special Categories: Provides extra protection for sensitive data like health information, political opinions, etc.
- Children's Data: Requires parental consent for processing data of children under 16 (or lower, as set by member states).
- Right to Explanation: Gives individuals the right to explanation about automated decision-making processes.

3.4.2. Use appropriate storage technologies and platforms

According to the Research Data Management (RDM) [4], which is mandatory for any Horizon Europe project, the data shall be stored in trusted repositories and provide open access to it ('as open as possible, as closed as necessary'),

Such repositories can be:

- Certified repositories, for example those with CoreTrustSeal [7], Nestor Seal DIN31644 [18], or ISO16363 [19] certifications.
- Domain-specific repositories (e.g. ZENODO [5]) that are internationally recognized, commonly used and endorsed by the research communities relevant to your project.
- General-purpose repositories or institutional repositories that, without official certification, present the essential characteristics of trusted repositories (e.g. security provisions, services for the creation of machine actionable metadata, long-term preservation of data, etc.).

The logging data generated should be stored in warehouses complying with the needs and requirements for the objectives of the data (validation/evaluation). As for the data transmission, many technologies can also be used to store data, such as:

Table 3: List of suitable storage technologies to store logging data

Storage Option	Ideal Use Case	Pros	Cons
Relational Databases (e.g. PostgreSQL, MySQL)	Structured log data, complex queries	- ACID compliance - Good for relationships - SQL querying	- Less scalable for high volumes - Schema changes can be challenging
NoSQL Databases (e.g., MongoDB, Cassandra)	Large volumes of unstructured data	- Highly scalable - Flexible schema - High write throughput	- Eventual consistency (in some cases) - Complex querying can be challenging
Elasticsearch	Full-text search, real-time analytics	- Powerful search capabilities - Real-time analytics - Scalable	- Resource intensive - Learning curve for optimization
Time-Series Databases (e.g. InfluxDB, TimescaleDB)	Time-stamped data, metrics	- Optimized for time-based queries - Efficient data compression	- Limited to time-series data

			- Less flexible for non-time data
Hadoop Ecosystem (HDFS, Hive)	Extremely large volumes, batch processing	- Highly scalable - Cost-effective for large data - Powerful analytics	- Complex setup - High latency for real-time queries
Cloud-based Solutions (e.g. AWS CloudWatch, Google Cloud Logging)	Cloud-native applications	- Managed service - Scalable - Integrated with cloud services	- Potential vendor lock-in - Can be costly at high volumes
Web-based Project Resources Repositories (e.g. Redmine, OPARU, ZENODO)	Structured and unstructured (raw) files storage	- Managed service - Easy to use	- File size and capacity limitations - Limited scalability
Specialized Log Management Tools (e.g. Splunk, Graylog)	Comprehensive log management	- Purpose-built for logs - Advanced analytics - User-friendly interfaces	- Can be expensive - Potential overkill for simple needs
Flat Files	Small-scale applications, temporary storage	- Simple and lightweight - No additional infrastructure needed	- Limited scalability - Difficult for complex queries

Depending on the needs for the validation and evaluation activities, **the storages could also be used as a support tool for smart queries, filtering, comparison and other tasks.** This is usually the case for high volumes of complex data, like large-scale C-ITS deployment projects such as C-MobILE [8] or C-ROADS [9].

PoDIUM LLS uses a mix of storage platforms and technologies. Most of the platform services are transmitting the logging data to Domain-specific repositories based on web technology like ZENODO (see section 3.4.2.1), Redmine and OPARU (from Universität Ulm and Technischen Hochschule Ulm) [10]. However, most of the vehicles, VRU devices and road infrastructure logs are temporarily stored in Flat Files locally on the same machines/devices, until they are finally uploaded to the trusted repositories.

According to the PoDIUM Living Labs plans, the validation and evaluation of such data will be carried by scripts and programs that will analyse the files stored in the different warehouses, not requiring smart features (e.g. smart queries, filtering, etc.) from the storages themselves.

3.4.2.1. ZENODO repository

ZENODO [5] is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citable, following FAIR principles.

For the EU Project Community, a specific repository within ZENODO named “Open repository for EU-funded research” has been created as pilot. PoDIUM project is officially part of this pilot repository [11] where most of the logs and results (incl. public deliverables, scientific publications, and publicly available results) will be published.

3.4.3. Establish access controls

Implement user authentication and authorization protocols to ensure only authorized personnel can access stored data is important to comply with data regulations as well as to ensure that data is not modified or deleted without control.

Authorization protocols work together with authentication to ensure that authenticated users only have access to the data they need for their specific roles. Role-based access control is a common approach, where access rights are assigned based on predefined roles within the project partnership. This should be complemented by the principle of least privilege, granting users the minimum levels of access required to perform their jobs.

Monitoring and logging are essential aspects of access control that should not be overlooked. All access attempts must be logged and regularly reviewed. Real-time monitoring systems can alert security teams to suspicious activities.

Combining these elements - strong authentication, granular authorization, and vigilant monitoring – can create a robust access control framework that significantly enhances the security of the stored data.

3.4.4. Implement a backup strategy

Logging data is crucial for the evaluation of systems. Any data loss would require repeating the tests, trials or deployments, which usually involves many resources (equipment, people, money, etc.).

Backing up data not only helps to minimize the impact of data loss due to failures, accidents or cyberattacks, but also helps compliance with data protection policies, providing necessary evidence for audits and legal proceedings.

We have adopted the good practice to **never store backups within the same system, organization or environment where the primary logged data is stored**. Currently, off-site storage (e.g. HDD/SSD) and cloud storage (e.g. Amazon S3, Google Cloud Storage, or Microsoft Azure Blob Storage) are commonly used as warehouses for backups.

4. Data Management in PoDIUM LLS

This section details the data collection and data storage relevant for the validation and evaluation of the PoDIUM systems architecture from each use case. They are defined as specifications, useful for the implementation of the data logging and the warehouses to be used during the integration, pre-evaluation testing, execution and evaluation phases.

For each use case, a functional diagram following D3.2 [1] specifications are shown with markers indicating the location of the data loggers. For each of those locations, which correspond to functional components of the architecture, a sub-section is present with the details of the data logging collected by the loggers placed that component, with the following fields:

- **Log data type:** Kind of main data recorded by the logger, which may correspond to the final desired data or a post-processing is required. Examples are “C-ITS messages”, “Video” or “Vehicle positioning / NMEA traces”.
- **Log format:** It could correspond to the logger data format or the final format (post-processed) ready for the storage. Examples are “CSV”, “JSON” or “Binary”.
- **Log data fields:** All fields recorded by the logger and/or required for the purpose of the logging (validation, evaluation, etc.). They usually contain an “ID”, “Sender”, “Receiver”, “Value” of the data, etc.
- **Logging event:** It specifies when the information is recorded. Details about periodicity/frequency are included.
- **Logging storage:** Mentions the storage name where this information is stored, either as temporary or final.
- **Relevancy:** For evaluation data, the identifier of the PoDIUM KPIs from D5.1 [12] (e.g. KPI_UC1_2) for which this data is relevant (either direct or indirectly) is introduced in this field. For validation data, the relevant component, scenario, interface or feature is mentioned. In many cases, the same data serves both purposes (validation and evaluation).

The full list of PoDIUM KPIs (deeply described in D5.1 [12]) are:

Table 4: PoDIUM Platform KPIs summary

Platform KPIs	
KPI_P_1 serviceAvailability	Service Availability, percentage of time the service is working with respect to the service being down; evaluated during demonstrations/experiments.
KPI_P_2 updateLatency	Latency of update messages to the DT with sensors/collective perception/data. It is the time gap between the event detection and its availability in a service DT (in cloud or MEC servers)
KPI_P_3 notificationLatency	Latency of notification messages from a service in the platform (MEC, Cloud) to arrive to its final consumer (CV, VRU).
KPI_P_4 processingDelay	The processing Time required between event (obstacle, VRU, road event) detection and the CCAM message availability for CAV to action, without accounting for transport delay.
KPI_P_5 comReliability	Communication message reliability. It describes how reliable is the PDI to deliver the messages to the users/vehicles/VRUs

KPI_P_6 SealedObject	This KPI represents the capability of the platform to protect sensible data/objects through the Trusted Platform Module (TPM) and its sealing/unsealing features.
KPI_P_7 LoadBootTime	This KPI evaluate the boot time with and without the Software Integrity Architecture.
KPI_P_8 LoadRunTime	This KPI evaluate the additional CPU utilization and memory consumption due to the Software Integrity Architecture.
KPI_P_9 RemoteAttestation	The Performance of the Remote Attestation protocol.

Table 5: PoDIUM UC1 KPIs summary

KPIs for UC1: Cooperative Corridor Management in City of Ulm	
KPI_UC1_1 Cooperative-Manoeuvre-CAV	The CAV on the blocked lane is able to pass the obstacle with a cooperative manoeuvre in at least 75% of the UC passes.
KPI_UC1_2 Cooperative-Manoeuvre-VRU	The VRU on the free lane is able to pass the obstacle in a complex traffic situation without getting into a dangerous situation. Additionally the CAV on the blocked lane is able to pass the obstacle with a cooperative manoeuvre.
KPI_UC1_3 Cooperative-Manoeuvre-MultiC	A scheduler can successfully make use of all currently available communication technologies to ensure communication between the Server and a CAV by redundancy.

Table 6: PoDIUM UC2 KPIs summary

KPIs for UC2: PDI for User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs	
KPI_UC2_1 Traffic_light_flow_improvement	The EVs find green light when they arrive at a controlled intersection.
KPI_UC2_2 Percentage_trips_ok_OD	Trips for which the beginning and end is correctly processed by TMS
KPI_UC2_3 Percentage_trips_ok_delay	Travel times across road links correctly processed
KPI_UC2_4 EV_priority_impact_on_traffic_reduction	Reduction of the extra red traffic light times for movements transversal to the EV corridor caused by guard times.
KPI_UC2_5 EV_percentage_successful_coop_manoeuvre	Cooperative manoeuvres correctly successfully managed.
KPI_UC2_6 Collision_with_VRU_risk_reaction_time_reduction	Average reduction of the response time by CV/CAVs when there is high risk of collision with a VRU

Table 7: PoDIUM UC3 KPIs summary

KPIs for UC3: Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor	
KPI_UC3_1 ServiceTime	Service delivery time (i.e. the reaction time at service layer) from time of incident detection or other “trigger” for updating the traffic strategy, until incident notification of CVs and updated traffic instructions (“manoeuvres”) received by CVs
KPI_UC3_2 CrossBorderInterruptionTime	Cross border interruption time (i.e. avoid interruption of service while switching from one country 5G network to the other)
KPI_UC3_3 ShuttleSpeed	MILLA’s CAV Shuttle needs to be capable to achieve 80km/h in SAE 4 autonomous driving conditions.
KPI_UC3_4 TrafficStrategiesImplementation	Evaluate the implementation of the traffic strategies by the CAV (autonomously) and the CV drivers (manually).

Table 8: PoDIUM UC4 KPIs summary

KPIs for UC4: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance	
KPI_UC4_1 VIMA_detection_performance	Performance of VRU Intersection Movement Assist (VIMA) application against false positive/negative
KPI_UC4_2 Vehicle_position_accuracy_urban	CAV positioning accuracy at the intersection
KPI_UC4_3 VIMA_crossing_manoeuvre_optimization	VIMA suggestions should lead to optimal manoeuvres to cross the intersection
KPI_UC4_4 VIMA_timing	End-to-end reaction time from VRU collision risk detection at RSU until notification at CAV.

Table 9: PoDIUM UC5 KPIs summary

KPIs for UC5: Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel	
KPI_UC5_1 Vehicle_position_accuracy_highway	CAV positioning accuracy on the highway
KPI_UC5_2 Vehicle_counting_accuracy	Accuracy % in the vehicles counting by entities that have this capability in PoDIUM UC5
KPI_UC5_3 Extended_perception_accuracy	Accuracy in perceiving vehicles in front

Another section dedicated to describing the Data Storages is present for each use cases. It provides details of the relevant warehouses mentioned in the “logging storage” from the previous section, including:

- **Warehouse type:** Kind of warehouse (e.g. local storage, external hard drive, cloud, etc.).
- **Storage structure:** How is the storage’s internal structure where the data is stored (e.g. folders, tables, buckets, no structured, etc.).
- **Access Security:** What type of security is implemented to manage the access to the data.
- **Access Interface:** How are the users accessing to the storage data.

4.1. UC1: Cooperative Corridor Management in City of Ulm

4.1.1. Data collection

In UC1, several data are collected for validation and evaluation of the components and the overall system. The location of the loggers is illustrated in the figure below.

The logging mainly focuses on the transmitted C-ITS messages at the road users, at the communication module of the MEC server and at the multi-connectivity scheduler to evaluate the communication technology. In addition, specific data like the processing time of the cooperative manoeuvre planning and the communication delay to the digital twin are logged. The loggers’ location is depicted in Figure 6. The data for the Use Case KPIs KPI_UC1_1, KPI_UC1_2 and KPI_UC1_3 (described in D5.1 [12]) are logged manually, as it is a qualitative evaluation done by a human expert.

Figure 6: UC1 functional diagram including loggers’ location

4.1.1.1. Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning

The cooperative manoeuvre planning logs the processing delay from receiving a new digital twin up to sending out a manoeuvre plan to the involved road users. The messages are logging to validate the performance KPIs. The data are logged only in the applicable scenarios (scenario 1 baseline, scenario 2). The delay information will be published in the publicly accessible OPARU and/or ZENODO repository.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Delay information	JSON	Timestamp, planning delay	Rx of each digital twin, Tx of each manoeuvre output	Local Bosch storage, OPARU/ZENODO	KPI_P_4

4.1.1.2. Digital Twin

The digital twin logs the communication delay of detection messages that are received from the infrastructure-based road user detection. The messages are logged to validate the scenarios and the performance KPIs. The data are logged only in the applicable scenarios (scenario 1 baseline, scenario 2).

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Delay information	JSON	Timestamp, detection delay	Rx of each detection msg	Local UULM storage	KPI_P_2

4.1.1.3. C-ITS Message and User Handling

The C-ITS Message and User Handling logs all C-ITS messages that are sent (Tx) and received (Rx). The messages are logged to validate the scenarios and the performance KPIs. Next to each message in binary and XML encoding, the timestamp, scenario ID, sender/receiver ID, and logging device ID are stored.

The message data will be published in the publicly accessible OPARU and/or ZENODO repository.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs	Binary, XML	Message content, scenario ID, timestamp, sender/receiver ID, logging device ID	Rx/Tx of each msg	Local UULM storage, OPARU/ZENODO	Scenario 1/2, KPI_P_1/3/5

4.1.1.4. Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) of UULM

The CAV of UULM logs all C-ITS messages that are sent (Tx) and received (Rx). The messages are logged to validate the scenarios and the performance KPIs. Next to each message in binary and XML encoding, the timestamp, scenario ID, sender/receiver ID, and logging device ID are stored.

The message data will be published in the publicly accessible OPARU and/or ZENODO repository.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs	Binary, XML	Message content, scenario ID, timestamp, sender/receiver ID, logging device ID	Rx/Tx of each msg	Local UULM storage, OPARU/ZENODO	Scenario 1/2, KPI_P_3/5

4.1.1.5. Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) of Bosch

The CAV of Bosch logs all C-ITS messages that are sent (Tx) and received (Rx) locally. The messages are logged to validate the scenarios and the performance KPIs. Next to each message in binary encoding, the meta data that is required for the KPI evaluation: message type, message ID, timestamp, scenario ID and station ID of sender/receiver are stored.

The meta data required for the KPI evaluation will be published in the publicly accessible OPARU and/or ZENODO repository.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs	Binary	Message content, scenario ID, timestamp, sender/receiver ID, logging device ID	Rx/Tx of each msg	Local Bosch storage	Scenario 1/2, KPI_P_3/5
C-ITS message metadata	XML	Message type, message ID, scenario ID, timestamp, sender/receiver ID, logging device ID	Rx/Tx of each msg	OPARU/ZENODO	Scenario 1/2, KPI_P_3/5

4.1.1.6. VRU Device & App

The Android App on the VRU Device from Nokia logs all C-ITS messages that are sent (Tx) and received (Rx). The messages are logged to validate the scenario and the performance KPIs to determine the latency. The C-ITS messages are stored in JSON format including timestamp, scenario ID, sender/receiver ID and logging device ID. The message data will be published in publicly available OPARU and/or ZENODO repository.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs	JSON	Message content, scenario ID, timestamp, sender/receiver ID, logging device ID	Rx/Tx of each msg	Local Nokia storage, OPARU/ZENODO	Scenario 1/2, KPI_P_3/5

4.1.1.7. Multi-Connectivity Scheduler

During logging experiments, the multi-connectivity Scheduler module of UDE logs data packet timestamps and specific packet IDs when sending and receiving through the different interfaces. The data packets are logged to validate the performance KPIs such as reliability. The logs will include for each recorded packet in binary and possibly PCAP encoding, the timestamp, packet ID, scenario ID, sender/receiver ID, the multi-connectivity communication interface.

The data will be published in the publicly accessible OPARU and/or ZENODO repository.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Data packets	Binary, PCAP	Data packet timestamp, packet ID, scenario ID, sender/receiver ID, multi-connectivity interface	Rx/Tx of each data packet	Local UDE storage, OPARU/ZENODO	Scenario 1/2, Multi-connectivity, KPI_P_3/5

4.1.2. Data storages

Some data will be stored locally at each German LL project partner, while some data will be made available publicly on OPARU and/or ZENODO.

4.1.2.1. Local storage at UULM

The data logged by the digital twin, the C-ITS Message and User Handling, and the Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) of UULM are stored in a local file-based storage at Ulm University with no external access.

Warehouse type	Local fileserver
Storage structure	Scenario- and time-based folders
Access Security	Local access only
Access interface	No public access

4.1.2.2. Local storage at Bosch

The data logged by the cooperative manoeuvre planning and the Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) of Bosch are stored in a local file-based storage at Bosch with no external access.

Warehouse type	Local fileserver
Storage structure	Scenario- and time-based folders
Access Security	Local access only
Access interface	No public access

4.1.2.3. Local storage at UDE

The data logged by the multi-connectivity scheduler module are stored in a local file-based storage at UDE with no external access.

Warehouse type	Local fileserver
Storage structure	Scenario- and time-based folders
Access Security	Local access only
Access interface	No public access

4.1.2.4. OPARU

The data logged by the German LL are published as a file-based archive at the public OPARU repository and/or ZENODO repository.

Warehouse type	Open Access file repository
Storage structure	File-based archive
Access Security	Public data only
Access interface	OPARU web interface

4.1.2.5. Local storage at UDE

The data logged by the multi-connectivity scheduler module are stored in a local file-based storage at UDE with no external access.

Warehouse type	Local fileserver
Storage structure	Scenario- and time-based folders
Access Security	Local access only
Access interface	No public access

4.1.2.6. ZENODO

The data logged by the German LL are published as a file-based archive at the public OPARU repository and/or the ZENODO repository.

Warehouse type	Open Access file repository
Storage structure	File-based archive
Security	Public access
Access interface	ZENODO web interface

4.2. UC2: PDI for User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs

4.2.1. Data collection

The data collection in UC2 is designed with two purposes: on one hand, the data collected will be used for the technical validation of the solution developed and deployed in the use case; on the other hand, the data will be the main inputs and evidences for the calculation of the KPIs, which are the basis for the evaluation of the success of the use case demonstration with regards of the objectives of the project. The loggers' location is depicted in Figure 7.

A set of important fields or metadata are missing from the next subsections where the logging details are described. In order to avoid redundancy, the common fields that most of all UC2 logging will include are:

- Timestamp: Moment when the data has been logged or captured.
- ID / msgID: Identifier of the data logged.

Once the metrics of a scenario are collected, these datasets will be uploaded to the warehouses with relevant metadata such as:

- UC: Relevant use case executed.
- Scenario: Relevant scenario executed.
- Device logging: Component or device where the logger is placed.

Figure 7: UC2 functional diagram including loggers' location

4.2.1.1. Traffic Management Control (TMC)

The Traffic Management Control component plays a crucial role in the different scenarios of UC2 and takes part in many important exchanges of information with the vehicles and road users. Therefore, logs collected at the TMC are required to calculate several KPIs for the use case performance evaluation:

- The TMC receives and processes CAM messages received from the vehicles and uses them for the functionalities of traffic management optimization (generate traffic metrics from movements of vehicles), priority to Emergency Vehicles (track movement of EVs and estimate arrival times to junctions). Logging this data is necessary to generate results for KPIs_UC2_1, 2, 4, 5 and 6.
- The TMC receives from the traffic controllers the status of traffic lights and uses it to check whether the EVs find green when they arrive at intersections, thus allowing the evaluation of the success of priority control, the purpose of KPI_UC2_1.
- The O-D matrices generated by the traffic optimization functionality of the TMC need to be logged and used to check the correctness of the functionality (the consistency of the O-D matrices with the data received from the vehicles), the purpose of KPI_UC2_2.
- The travel times and delays per road segment generated by the traffic optimization functionality of the TMC need to be logged and used to check the correctness of the functionality (the consistency of the O-D matrices with the data received from the vehicles), the purpose of KPI_UC2_3.

- The events of activation and deactivation of priority for EV at intersections, an action performed by the TMS itself, need to be logged to calculate KPI_UC2_4, estimating the impact of an ‘excess of green light’ for the EV (significantly more than needed to cross the intersection) on the rest of users of the road network.

In addition to this, some logs are addressed to the calculation of platform KPIs. Most of these logs will store the messages exchanged with other services or with the connected vehicles and will allow the evaluation of the reliability (KPI_P_5) and performance (KPI_P_2, KPI_P_3) of the communication mechanism, as well as the processing delay introduced by the services themselves (KPI_P_4).

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
CAM from vehicles	CSV	lat/lon, stationID, speed, long accel, origin point, destination point, vehicle type	On all Rx	Redmine, Local storage	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_UC2_1/2/4/5/6, KPI_P_2
Traffic Light status	CSV	trafficLightGroupId, colour, lat/lon	On color change	Redmine, Local storage	Scenario 1, KPI_UC2_1
O-D matrices	CSV	Origin, destination, n# of trips, average travel time, average distance run, time period	Periodically	Redmine, TMC warehouse	Scenario 2, KPI_UC2_2
Travel times per road segment	CSV	Road segment, n# of trips, average travel time, average delay, delay sum, average speed, time period	Periodically	Redmine, TMC warehouse, Local storage	Scenario 2, KPI_UC2_3
Start and end traffic light priority	CSV	trafficLightGroupId, lat/lon, activation/deactivation	On priority changed	Redmine, Local storage	Scenario 1, KPI_UC2_4
Availability	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s	Redmine	KPI_P_1
Incident received from TMS	CSV	Timestamp	On incident Rx	Redmine	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_P_2/4
DENM Message sent to CITS	CSV	stationID, detectionTime, referenceTime, validityDuration, lat/lon, causeCode, sequenceNumber, relevanceDistance	On message sent	Redmine	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_P_3/4/5

4.2.1.2. Connected and Automated, Connected Conventional and Emergency Vehicles

Some evaluation KPIs of UC2 involve checking the effect of warnings sent by the PoDIUM services to the vehicles (as DENM messages) in terms of presentation to the driver and/or reaction by the automated driving control of the vehicle.

In case specific logs are provided by the CAV/CV (for example, a log of the presentation of information in the HMI display, or of the switching to safe mode for the CAV), they will be used; otherwise, the change of trajectory of the vehicle resulting from the vehicle reaction to DENM message may be identified from processing the CAM messages sent by the vehicle during the reaction.

In addition to this, some logs are addressed to the calculation of platform KPIs. Most of these logs will store the messages exchanged with other services or with the connected vehicles and will allow the evaluation of the reliability (KPI_P_5) and performance (KPI_P_2, KPI_P_3) of the communication mechanism, as well as the processing delay introduced by the services themselves (KPI_P_4).

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs (CAM msgs)	CSV	lat/lon, stationID, speed, long accel, origin point, destination point, vehicle type, CAM JSON	Once Tx and Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_UC2_1/2/4/5/6, KPI_P_3/4/5

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs (DENM msgs)	CSV	EventType, EventLocation (lat/lon), DENM JSON	Once Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_UC2_1/6, KPI_P_3/4/5
HMI information	CSV	WarningType, Seq. Number, EventLocation, DistanceToEvent, EventInformation	Periodically every 300ms	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_UC2_5/6, KPI_P_3/4
Beacons	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s since startup	Redmine	KPI_P_1
Video stream	raw	Internal and external video stream	Continuous logging (30-day max.)	Internal Hard drive	Scenario 1/2/3
Vehicle position	CSV	pos lat/lon/alt, vehicle orientation, GNSS quality, roll/pitch/yaw, east angle, angular velocities (roll/pitch/yaw), long. acceleration	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_UC2_4/5/6/7
Vehicle movement	CSV	longitudinal speed, longitudinal acceleration, driving direction	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2/3
Vehicle core	CSV	lateral door / turn indicators / brake light / reverse light / low beam light / day light / blinker state, battery level, odometer, engine rotation speed	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2/3
Vehicle perception	CSV	safety zone is activated, total number of detected traffic lights (V2X & camera)	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2/3
Vehicle autonomous data	CSV	driving mode, current goal name, driver takes control of the shuttle, top level diagnostic state	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2/3

4.2.1.3. C-ITS Message and User Handling

The Gateway, as a middleware for the C-ITS messages between the vehicles/RSUs and the TMC/Digital Twin, logs all information passing through both ways. It is mainly involved in the validation of all UC2 scenarios, which involve the C-ITS messages for the events and manoeuvres.

It also logs the incoming requests from the TMC to generate the C-ITS messages to be disseminated to the field stations. All logs to be produced by C-ITS services in UC2 will be used for the calculation of platform KPIs. Most of these logs will store the messages exchanged with other services or with the connected vehicles and will allow the evaluation of the reliability (KPI_P_5) and performance (KPI_P_2, KPI_P_3) of the communication mechanism, as well as the processing delay introduced by the services themselves (KPI_P_4).

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Beacons	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s since startup	Redmine	KPI_P_1
C-ITS msgs (CAM msgs)	CSV	lat/lon, stationID, speed, long accel, origin point, destination point, vehicle type, CAM JSON	Every message Rx from CAV/CVs and Tx to TMC	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_P_3/4/5
C-ITS msgs (DENM msgs)	CSV	stationID, detectionTime, referenceTime, lat/lon, causeCode validityDuration, sequenceNumber, relevanceDistance, DENM JSON	Every message Rx from RM/TMC and Tx to CAV/CVs	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_P_2/3/4/5

4.2.1.4. Risk Management (RM)

All logs to be produced by RM services in UC2 will be used for the calculation of platform KPIs. Most of these logs will store the messages exchanged with other services or with the connected vehicles and will allow the evaluation of the reliability (KPI_P_5) and performance (KPI_P_2, KPI_P_3) of the

communication mechanism, as well as the processing delay introduced by the services themselves (KPI_P_4).

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Availability	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s	Redmine	KPI_P_1
VRU detected	CSV	Timestamp	Every detection	Redmine	Scenario 3, KPI_P_2/4
C-ITS msgs (DENM msgs)	CSV	stationID, detectionTime, referenceTime, validityDuration, lat/lon, causeCode, sequenceNumber, relevanceDistance	Every message sent to the Gateway	Redmine	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_P_2/3/4/5
C-ITS msgs (CAM msgs)	CSV	lat/lon, stationID, speed, long accel, origin point, destination point, vehicle type	Every message Rx from the Gateway	Local storage (temporary), Redmine	Scenario 1/2/3, KPI_P_2

4.2.1.5. VRU mobile app

All logs collected from VRU mobile App will be used for the calculation of platform KPIs. Most of these logs will store the messages exchanged with other services or with the connected vehicles and will allow the evaluation of the reliability (KPI_P_5) and performance (KPI_P_2, KPI_P_3) of the communication mechanism, as well as the processing delay introduced by the services themselves (KPI_P_4).

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Warning for Collision risk with CAV/CV	CSV	detectionTime, sendTime, lat/lon, receptionTime	Every message Rx	Firebase	Scenario 3, KPI_P_3/4/5

4.2.2. Data storages

This section describes each of the warehouses/storages available for the UC, including private storages for validation of the scenarios/functions, evaluation of KPIs and public data (e.g. ZENODO).

4.2.2.1. TMC warehouse

The TMC calculates results (O-D matrices, travel times and delays per road segment) within traffic optimization scenario and stores them in tables of an SQL Server database. These data are completely anonymised, not being possible to identify the road users whose data were originally received, and statistically treated.

Warehouse type	Relational database in-house (SQLServer)
Storage structure	Tables
Access Security	User-password authentication
Access interface	SQL

4.2.2.2. Local storage

Some evaluation KPIs, especially those related to the evaluation of the generation of traffic metrics functionality, imply processing a great quantity of logs generated by the service. Due to the volume of logs generated and the complexity of the processing of these logs for calculating the KPIs, those will be stored locally at the PoDIUM cloud service platform, in CSV files within the server where TMC and RM services run, inside a folder that will be mounted as a volume inside the docker containers of the services. Only authorized technical personnel of the project will have access to these files, which will be the inputs of suitable processing tools that shall generate the KPI results.

Warehouse type	In-house platform local storage
Storage structure	Folders containing CSV

Access Security	User-password credentials for accessing files and folders, restricted to users with appropriate privileges
Access interface	Manual access

4.2.2.3. Redmine

Logs that can be shared within the project and can be directly processed to obtain values for the KPIs will be uploaded to the Redmine document repository of the project. This repository is secured by means of users and passwords and can only be accessed by users with suitable privileges.

Warehouse type	Redmine (project document repository)
Storage structure	Folder containing CSV
Access Security	User-password credentials for accessing files and folders, restricted to users with appropriate privileges
Access interface	Manual access

4.2.2.4. ZENODO

Shareable data from the scenarios (mainly C-ITS messages exchanged between the road users and the PDI) will be published in ZENODO.

Warehouse type	Open Access file repository
Storage structure	File-based archive
Security	Public access
Access interface	ZENODO web interface

4.2.2.5. Firebase

The VRU mobile app will generate its logs and send them to a Google Firebase database, where they will be centralised and accessible for processing them.

Warehouse type	Relational database in the cloud
Storage structure	Collections
Access Security	User-password credentials
Access interface	Google Firebase API

4.3. UC3: Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor

4.3.1. Data collection

The data collection for UC3 is meant to help both the validation and evaluation of the systems. As shown in Figure 8 (below), the loggers are located in all platform systems (except in the Shuttle Management) with the objective of analysing not only the source and destination of the data for the scenarios, but also the intermediate steps.

The logging is focused on the exchanged C-ITS messages in general, but since in the upper layers of the platform the type of data is proprietary (no ETSI standard), some logging is also present there. The use of identifiers to relate raw data that it becomes C-ITS data (or other way around) is advisable. Loggers are also present in all vehicle types, as well as in the C-V2X infrastructure (RSUs) and the VRU device since they all exchange C-ITS data within the scenarios.

A set of important fields or metadata are missing from the next subsections where the logging details is described. In order to avoid redundancy, the common fields that most of all UC3 logging will include are:

- Timestamp: Moment when the data has been logger or captured.
- ID / msgID: Identifier of the data logged.

Once the metrics of a scenario are collected, these datasets will be uploaded to the warehouses with relevant metadata such as:

- UC: Relevant use case executed.
- Scenario: Relevant scenario executed.
- Device logging: Component or device where the logger is placed.

Figure 8: UC3 functional diagram including loggers' location

4.3.1.1. Traffic Management Centre (TMC) & Mobility Hub

The TMC architecture in UC3 is designed with 2 levels, the Local TMC in the edge (MEC) and the Global TMC in the cloud. The two levels intercommunicate and collaborate for the generation of traffic strategies. The Global TMC does not have any external interfaces with other components; only with the Local TMC. Therefore, the loggers are valid for both levels, as they cover the (also common) input and output interfaces of the TMC.

Logged Input & Output data to/from the TMC:

- Input: Detected obstacles (from the LDM, and from the VA).

- Input: Aggregated traffic flow data per highway section (average number of vehicles, average speed).
- Output: Traffic Strategies sent to the Gateway (logged in the C-ITS message handling).

The Mobility Hub is a data handler component. It receives the live feed input from the traffic cameras and distributes it to the Video Analytics (VA) module. Then receives the output of the VA processed data and sends it to the Local TMC.

Logged data to/from the Mobility Hub:

- Video Analytics data (processed camera feeds).
- Camera feed (optional, only when needed, e.g. for initial system validation).

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Obstacle detection (from DENM)	CSV	Detection timestamp, lat/lon, ObstacleID	Once Rx by the TMC from the LDM	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_2/4
Obstacle detection (from Video Analytics)	CSV	Detection timestamp, Vehicle ID, lat/lon, lane number, vehicle speed, CameraID, VehicleType, VehicleColor, FPS of detection, Confidence of detection, complete VA data	Once Rx by the TMC from the Mobility Hub	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_2/4
POST /DELETE of Traffic strategies	JSON	HighwaySegment, MaxSpeed, DistanceFrontVehicle, Lane blocked, strategyId, status (POST / DELETE)	Once sent from the TMC to the GW	Redmine	Scenario 1/2, KPI_P_3/4
POST /DELETE of incidents	JSON	causeCodeType, validityDuration, obstacleType, lat/lon, hazardId, status (POST / DELETE)	Once sent from the TMC to the GW	Redmine	Scenario 1/2, KPI_P_3/4
Camera feed	MP4 video	CameraID, CameraLocation, CameraDirection, Video stream	When logging is activated manually	Internal	Scenario 1/2
Beacons	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s since startup	Redmine	KPI_P_1

4.3.1.2. Connected and Automated Vehicle & Connected Conventional Vehicles

All vehicles involved in UC3 are logging two main types of data:

- **C-ITS Messages:** In general, all transmitted and received C-ITS messages are logged to validate the scenarios and the performance KPIs. In particular, the logged CAM messages will be recorded to properly evaluate the behaviour of the autonomous and connected vehicles upon the different traffic strategies generated by the road operator.

The logging of the C-ITS messages contains a set of fixed fields which are:

- Technology: The technology by which the messages has been transmitted or received.
- stationID: The ETSI identifier of the component that has generated the message.
- Source IP: IP of the sender.
- Destination IP: IP of the receiver.
- ASN1: Hex ASN1 format of the message from Facilities layer (when available).
- Type: C-ITS message type (e.g. CAM, DENM, IVIM, etc.).

These fixed fields will help validate the interfaces exchanging ITS Messages and detect issues or undesired behaviours of the system for all scenarios.

- **Network status:** UC3 aims to evaluate interruption time (KPI_UC3_2) from a cross-border roaming situation. For that, periodic network metrics will be logged from each router/modem used within the vehicles.

All vehicle’s logs are expected to be stored in an internal PoDIUM repository but also shared with the community via ZENODO.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs (CAM msgs)	CSV	lat/lon, stationID, speed, long accel, origin point, destination point, vehicle type, CAM JSON	Once Tx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_3/4, KPI_P_3/4/5
C-ITS msgs (DENM msgs)	CSV	EventType, EventLocation (lat/lon), DENM JSON	Once Tx and Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_3/4/5
C-ITS msgs (IVIM msgs)	CSV	SpeedTarget, RoadSegments, IVIM JSON	Once Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_3/4/5
C-ITS msgs (MCM msgs)	CSV	BlockedLane, RoadSegments, TargetDistance, MCM JSON	Once Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_3/4/5
C-ITS msgs (all of them)	CSV	Serialized message (as it arrives)	Once Tx and Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine	Scenario 1, Scenario 2, KPI_P_3/4/5
HMI information	CSV	WarningType, Seq. Number, EventLocation, DistanceToEvent, EventInformation	Periodically every 300ms	Redmine	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_4, KPI_P_3/4
Network status (ping)	CSV	Timestamp, Round Trip Time to the MEC	Periodically every 200ms	Redmine, ZENODO	KPI_UC3_2, Cross-border roaming
Beacons	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s since startup	Redmine	Scenario 1, KPI_P_1
Video stream	raw	Internal and external video stream	Continuous (30-day max.)	Internal Hard drive	Scenario 1/2
Vehicle status	CSV	globalHealth, behaveHealth, driveDirection	On state change	Redmine	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_4
Vehicle position	CSV	pos lat/lon/alt, vehicle orientation, GNSS quality, roll/pitch/yaw, east angle, angular velocities (roll/pitch/yaw), long. acceleration	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2, Scenario 2
Vehicle movement	CSV	longitudinal speed, longitudinal acceleration, driving direction	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2, KPI_UC3_3
Vehicle core	CSV	lateral door / turn indicators / brake light / reverse light / low beam light / day light / blinker state, battery level, odometer, engine rotation speed	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2
Vehicle perception	CSV	safety zone is activated, n# of detected traffic lights (V2X & camera)	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2
Vehicle autonomous data	CSV	driving mode, current goal name, driver takes control of the shuttle, top level diagnostic state	While AD mode ON	Internal	Scenario 1/2

4.3.1.3. C-ITS Message and User Handling

The Gateway, as a middleware for the C-ITS messages between the vehicles/RSUs and the TMC/Digital Twin, logs all information passing through both ways. It is mainly involved in the validation of the UC3 Scenario 2 which involves the C-ITS messages for the events and strategies.

Such C-ITS messages are logged with the same fixed fields as for the Connected and Automated Vehicle & Connected Conventional Vehicles logging. It also logs the incoming requests from the TMC to generate the C-ITS messages to be disseminated to the field stations.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs (CAM msgs)	CSV	Speed, Location (lat/lon), longitudinal acceleration, origin/dest. Points, vehicle type, CAM JSON	Once Tx and Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 1/2, KPI_UC3_2/4, KPI_P_5
C-ITS msgs (DENM msgs)	CSV	EventType, EventLocation (lat/lon), validityDuration, relevanceDistance, sequenceNumber, DENM JSON	When Tx and Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_3/4/5
C-ITS msgs (IVIM msgs)	CSV	SpeedTarget, RoadSegments, IVIM JSON	Once Tx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_3/5
C-ITS msgs (MCM msgs)	CSV	BlockedLane, RoadSegments, TargetDistance, MCM JSON	Once Tx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_3/5
C-ITS msgs (CPM msgs)	CSV	Direction, Speed, Location (lat/lon) and type of perceived objects, CPM JSON	Once Tx and Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2 KPI_P_1/3/5
C-ITS msgs (all of them)	CSV	Serialized message (as it arrives)	Once Tx and Rx (C-V2X & 5G)	Redmine	Scenario 1/2, KPI_P_3/5
C-ITS msgs (DENM VRU Risk Alert)	CSV	Speed, Location (lat/lon), Risk Alert - DENM JSON	Once Tx and Rx (5G)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 1, KPI_P_3/5
Traffic Strategies	CSV	RoadSegments, StrategyType, MaxSpeed, DistanceFrontVehicle, LaneBlocked, StrategyId, Operation (POST/DELETE)	Once Rx from the TMC	Redmine	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_3
Road Hazard Situation	CSV	EventLocation (lat/lon), ValidityDuration, CauseCode, HazardId, Operation (POST/DELETE)	Once Rx from TMC	Redmine	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_1, KPI_P_3
Beacons	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s since startup	Redmine	Scenario 1, KPI_P_1

4.3.1.4. Digital Twin (LDM)

The Digital Twin (DT) consists of a Local Dynamic Map (LDM) that stores and updates the state (location, speed, identifiers, etc.) of various road objects (vehicles, VRUs, road obstacles, etc.). It has three main functions:

- Record all incoming data from the vehicles.
- Maintain updated data despite short interruptions in incoming messages from the vehicles (e.g., due to cross-border situations) using an estimator in the "Intelligent LDM updaters".
- Provide this data to other applications, such as the TMC or the Awareness Distributor.

The necessary logs for this DT/LDM include its inputs and outputs. Inputs are the messages generated by the vehicles, already logged by the Gateway and specified in the previous section. Outputs, which need to be logged by the DT/LDM, will consist of pairs formed by all requests the DT/LDM receives from other applications and the content of the replies it provides.

By comparing the DT/LDM's responses with the actual positions of the vehicles (obtained from the logs generated by these vehicles), we can compute metrics such as cross-border interruption time at the application level or the error in vehicle position estimation.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
DT data entries	CSV	Request/Reply containing: StationID, Speed, Location (lat/lon), Technology, density of vehicles in a road segment	Every time the DT receives a query	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 2, KPI_UC3_2, KPI_P_2
Beacons	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s since startup	Redmine	Scenario 1, KPI_P_1

4.3.1.5. Shuttle Passenger app

The main loggers are part of the functional components in the system, specifically within the application software that handles both mobile and cloud API requests. These loggers are responsible for capturing detailed request information at different stages:

- **Mobile Requests Logger:** Located within the mobile application, it logs every request made by the user from their mobile device to the cloud.
- **Cloud API Requests Logger:** Located within the cloud infrastructure, it logs every request received from the mobile application.

The logging system captures the following fields for each request, ensuring consistent and comprehensive data collection:

- **User ID:** Helps in identifying the user making the request.
- **Datetime:** Provides the exact time when the request was made or received, useful for tracking and debugging.
- **Type Request:** Indicates what kind of operation the request is performing (e.g., GET, POST).
- **Endpoint:** Specifies the API endpoint being accessed, aiding in identifying which part of the system is being interacted with.
- **Spent Time (ms):** Measures the performance by logging the time taken to process the request, critical for performance monitoring.
- **Request Code:** Shows the outcome of the request, which is important for error handling and debugging.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Mobile requests	Text log	User ID, Datetime, Type request, Endpoint, spent time (ms), request code	At every request made for the user mobile app to the cloud	Internal	Scenario 1
Cloud API requests	Text log	User ID, Datetime, Type request, Endpoint, spent time (ms), request code	At every request Rx	Internal	Scenario 1
Beacons	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s since startup	Redmine	Scenario 1, KPI_P_1

4.3.1.6. Shuttle Management

The logger will be located in the ENIDE cloud in the route management application. All interactions carried out with the MILLA cloud will be logged. The relevant data fields logged are:

- **User ID:** Unique identifier for the user.
- **Datetime:** Timestamp of when the request was received.
- **Type Request:** Type or nature of the request.
- **Endpoint:** Specific endpoint of the API being accessed.
- **Spent Time (ms):** Time taken to process the request in milliseconds.

- **Request Code:** Code representing the result or status of the request.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Requests	TXT	Timestamp, Type request, Endpoint, spent time (ms), Request code	Every request Tx to MILLA Cloud	Internal	Scenario 1, KPI_P_4
Beacons	CSV	Timestamp	Every 10s since startup	Redmine	Scenario 1, KPI_P_1

4.3.1.7. C-V2X / ITS-G5 Roadside Units

RSUs are responsible for transparently forwarding encoded messages to and from vehicles and the Gateway using their C-V2X radio interface. Although this operation is quite simple, in cases of high volume of traffic, it has been tested that any other operation in the RSU, as logging, decreases the performance of the RSU. For this reason, during the pre-evaluation testing, we will perform some logging, nevertheless this logging will be deactivated during the real test.

These logs will contain the whole encoded message and the direction of the transmission, from the Gateway to the vehicles or vice versa.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs	CSV	Encoded data message, timestamp, direction	On Tx and Rx (C-V2X)	Redmine, ZENODO	Scenario 1/2, KPI_UC3_1/2, KPI_P_5

4.3.2. Data storages

UC3 plans to log data from remote, roadside and mobile components (e.g. VRUs, CAV, CV, etc.) internally, storing the logs in the same machines/places where the functionality runs. Platform components are able to report the logs automatically to external warehouses (e.g. Redmine/ZENODO).

4.3.2.1. Redmine

Most of the platform components are logging automatically in Redmine, the PoDIUM document repository. Vehicles' logs are also uploaded to Redmine after a manual extraction.

Warehouse type	Redmine (project document repository)
Storage structure	Folder containing CSV
Access Security	User-password credentials for accessing files and folders, restricted to users with appropriate privileges
Access interface	Manual access

All logs are going to be stored in specific folders based on the logging component, with files named as YYYY-MM-DD_HH:mm:ss_SCENARIO_SOURCE_RESPONSIBLE where:

YYYY is the current year (e.g. 2024), MM is the current month number (e.g. 09), DD is the current day number (05), SCENARIO is the identifier of the scenario or use case (e.g. SPEED_STRATEGY), SOURCE is the component generator of the logfile (e.g. MILLA_CAV) and the RESPONSIBLE is the partner responsible to this log, ensuring coherence, consistency and cleanness (e.g. IDIADA).

Naming the logs files with such structure will ease the extraction for analysis.

4.3.2.2. ZENODO

Shareable data from the scenarios (mainly C-ITS messages exchanged between the road users and the PDI) are going to be published in ZENODO.

Warehouse type	Open Access file repository
Storage structure	File-based archive
Security	Public access
Access interface	ZENODO web interface

4.4. UC4: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance

4.4.1. Data collection

Logging necessary for UC4 as well as for UC5 has been considered as measurement of the different event communication messages, from which all logging information will come from. Basically, logs will contain the UC id, location, scenario and timestamp of the event, but the messages are mostly related with the exchange of several information extracted from CCAM messages and its trace information such as message timestamp, timestamp on which it was originated and a hash of the message in order to trace the same message across other logs taken.

Figure 9: UC4 functional diagram including loggers' location

4.4.1.1. Connected Automated Vehicle - CAV

A dedicated logging system on the vehicle records all the relevant data from the internal vehicle network and components, including the data from/to the C-ITS component. The logging system is managed by CRF.

Independently, a C-ITS logging system on the OBU records the data relevant to the V2X messages (CAM, DENM, IVIM, SPAT, MAP, CPM) exchanged with the PoDIUM Platform. This C-ITS logging system is managed by LINKS.

The objective is to evaluate how the CAV is assisted by the Podium platform when approaching an intersection, with special focus on VRU safety and precedence management.

During UC4 tests, these data will be logged at CAV

- The exchanged V2X messages with the Podium platform, at the CAV OBU (Tx, Rx messages)
- Positioning and positioning quality with a dedicated in-vehicle logger
- Data related to CAV motion, speed and vehicle dynamics with a dedicated in-vehicle logger
- HMI data which include, object (VRU) identification, warning, indications and also manoeuvre suggestions that are meant for the AD function (and actuated manually in the pilot)

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs	CSV	stationID, msgType, md5sum, hexStr, msgtimestamp	On message Tx/Rx	Local Server at LINKS and subset on ZENODO	Scenario 1/2, KPI_P_3
C-ITS msgs	CSV	stationID, msgType, md5sum, hexStr, msgtimestamp	On message Tx/Rx	Local Server at LINKS and subset on ZENODO	KPI_P_2/3/5
Availability	CSV	Timestamp, service_status	Every 10 s on OBU	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_1
CAN	BINARY	stationID, msgType, md5sum, hexStr, msgtimestamp	When C-ITS msgs are relevant	Local Server at CRF	KPI_P_2, KPI_UC4_1/4
CAV Positioning	BINARY	Latitude, Longitude, SemimajorAxis, SemiminorAxis	Periodic	Local Server at CRF	KPI_UC4_2
Manoeuvre data	BINARY	Speed, acceleration, yaw rate, etc.	Periodic	Local Server at CRF	KPI_UC4_3
Application / HMI data	BINARY	VRU identification (X, Y) driver warning and suggestions	Event triggered (VRU crossing)	Local Server at CRF	KPI_UC4_1

4.4.1.2. Digital Twin

The Digital Twin handles messages incoming from vehicles and their increased trust and higher truthfulness versions. In practical, the digital twin logging records the messages and their timestamps in order to calculate the time used by the VIMA service to produce a IVIM output. Other logs with traffic control with the municipality of Turin are taken to verify the real-time availability of SPAT/MAP messages.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs	ASN1	MsgType, md5sum, hexStr, msgtimestamp	On message Rx/Tx	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_4, KPI_P_2
Availability	CSV	Timestamp, service_status	Every 10 s	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_1

4.4.1.3. C-ITS Message Handling

Being the central point where C-ITS messages (CAM, DENM, IVIM, SPAT, MAP, CPM) transit, the logging is driven by the different messages captured when vehicles interact and when information is produced

by SPUs. Therefore, logs are linked to these interfaces where messages are directed to get granular timing information.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs	CSV	StationID, msgType, md5sum, hexStr, msgtimestamp	On message Rx/Tx	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_3, KPI_P_5
Availability	CSV	Timestamp, service_status	Every 10 s	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_1

4.4.1.4. Software Integrity

Most of KPIs are measured without the need of logging since the events being measured are low-level, so they are only captured on console, such as the booting timing. Instead, attestation interactions and user handling are measured via logging during operation, so SWint logs this information and its timings.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Attestation interactions	CSV	SeqID, duration	On message Rx/Tx	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_9
Availability	CSV	Timestamp, service_status	Every 10 s	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_1

4.4.1.5. Cooperative Manoeuvre Planning (VIMA)

The service on top of digital twin is the VIMA service (comprised in cooperative manoeuvres planning of the PODIUM architecture). Its logs bring information regarding the time required to perform operations of calculating the IVIM timings in real-time, such as KPI_P_4. In this case the VIMA keeps the hash of the original CCAM message that triggered the generation of an IVIM. That information is necessary to locate within the Digital Twin C-ITS log the message timestamp required to calculate the processing delay.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS msgs	JSON	orig-CCAM-msg-md5, msgType, md5sum, hexStr	On message Rx/Tx	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_4
Availability	CSV	Timestamp, service_status	Every 10 s	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_1

4.4.1.6. Roadside Units

The roadside units log C-ITS messages received on short range interfaces and log also their CPMs produced because of the detection. These are useful when calculating the update latency of detected events with the camera and LIDAR and tracing of other events.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
Availability	CSV	Timestamp, service_status	Every 10 s	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_1
C-ITS msgs	CSV	StationID, msgType, md5sum, hexStr, msgtimestamp	On message Rx/Tx	Local Server at LINKS	KPI_P_2, KPI_P_5

4.4.2. Data storages

Italian Partners have decided a pragmatic approach of storing the test data compressed locally on devices for redundancy and recovering them based on their naming structure by using a test run identifier, in such a way that tests can be traced not only by time and date but also with file name. Files are then stored on a local PC for processing data for every run.

4.4.2.1. Local server at LINKS

A host has been prepared in LINKS premises to maintain a copy of the logs generated. The logs will be stored in their original files decompressed using an ext4 filesystem. Access is restricted via ssh through a VPN only by LINKS’ authorized employees.

Warehouse type	Linux ext4 file system inside LINKS premises in Turin, Italy
Storage structure	“Folders-scenario/folder-run/time-component-type”
Access Security	Private access to users
Access interface	“SSH+VPN”

4.4.2.2. ZENODO

The data logged in CSV format regarding C-ITS messages are published as files or archives at the public ZENODO repository as established by the project. Given that the C-ITS messages might be traced along other message logs, disclosing information about the vehicle, the partners prefer to anonymize the vehicle identifiers participating to the tests.

Warehouse type	Open Access file repository
Storage structure	File-based archive
Security	Public access
Access interface	ZENODO web interface

4.5. UC5: Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel

4.5.1. Data collection

This use case inherits most of the logging already defined for UC4 given the vehicle, RSU and edge platform instances. The difference relies on the Risk Management elaborations and the fact that no VRUs are present and other connected vehicles send data (but not logging).

In UC5 CRF will adapt its dedicated logging system to the specific PoDIUM needs. Similarly to UC4, the system records all the relevant data from the internal vehicle network and components, but it also includes V2X received/transmitted messages, as the OBU in UC5 is managed by CRF and not by LINKS as in UC4. Therefore the logs not dealing directly with the CAV can be considered as already described in UC4 and are not repeated here. An example of this is KPI_P_1 is reported in CAV here since it is performed by LINKS’ OBU in UC4 and here it is on CRF’s OBU; KPI_P_4-processingDelay is already measured in UC4 and in UC5 the only difference is that it is measured by the RMT (that only appears on UC5) and not the VIMA (which belongs to UC4). RSUs and C-ITS message handling would appear also in UC4 so their logs are not repeated identically here.

Figure 10: UC5 functional diagram including loggers location

4.5.1.1. Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV)

The main scope of UC5 tests is to evaluate cooperative ADAS and AD functions inside and outside of tunnels: in such environments, in-vehicle positioning and timing would be impacted by the absence of GNSS, but Podium offers technical solution to keep position and time references. The goal of the pilot is to measure the performance of positioning/timing, also in relation to the CAV functions impacted.

The data logged include:

- The exchanged V2X messages between the vehicles and with the PoDIUM platform, at the CAV OBU (Tx, Rx messages)
- Positioning and positioning quality (note that this is also logged in UC4 for performance evaluation in urban environment)
- Data related to speed and vehicle dynamics
- Data related to the perceived objects, by sensors and CPM
- Application data which include warning, indications and also manoeuvre suggestions that are meant for the AD function (and actuated manually in the pilot).

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
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V2X messages	BINARY	V2X messages: CAN, DENM, IVIM, CPM	On message Rx/Tx	Local Server at CRF and subset on ZENODO	KPI_UC5_1/3, KPI_P_2/3/4/5
Availability	CSV	Timestamp, service_status	Every 10 s	Local Server at CRF	KPI_P_1
Perceived Objects	BINARY	X, Y position of objects	Object detection/update (sensors, CPM)	Local Server at CRF	KPI_UC5_3
CAV Positioning data	BINARY	Latitude, Longitude, SemimajorAxis, SemimajorOrientation, SemiminorAxis	Periodic	Local Server at CRF	KPI_UC5_1/3
CAV manoeuvre data	BINARY	Speed, acceleration, yaw rate, etc.	Periodic	Local Server at CRF	KPI_UC5_3
CAV application data	BINARY	Driver warning, lane change suggestions, ADAS/AD level engaged/disengaged, target speed, etc.	Event triggered	Local Server at CRF	KPI_UC5_1

4.5.1.2. Risk Management in Tunnel

The services around digital twin are the Risk Management service and the C-ITS broker. The digital twin and the C-ITS Broker services were explained for UC4. The RM logs bring information regarding the time required to perform the risk calculation operations, such as KPI_P_4.

Log data type	Log format	Log data fields	Logging event	Logging storage	Relevancy
C-ITS	JSON	orig-CCAM-msg-md5, msgType, md5sum, hexStr	On msg Rx/Tx	Local Server	KPI_P_4
Availability	CSV	Timestamp, service_status	Every 10 s	Local Server	KPI_P_1

4.5.2. Data storages

4.5.2.1. Local server at CRF

A local server at CRF will maintain a copy of the logs generated. The logs will be stored in their original files. Access is restricted to CRF authorized employees.

Warehouse type	Linux ext4 file system
Storage structure	“Folders-scenario/folder-run/time-component-type”
Access Security	Private access to users
Access interface	“SSH+VPN”

4.5.2.2. ZENODO

The V2X messages during the use case execution, properly anonymized, will be also available on ZENODO.

Warehouse type	Open Access file repository
Storage structure	File-based archive
Security	Public access
Access interface	ZENODO web interface

5. Conclusions

For this deliverable D4.1, the detailed deployment, integration and pre-evaluation testing for each of the PoDIUM use cases has been documented. These plans are essential for a successful operation and execution of the UCs' scenarios, as well as for a successful completion of the project's objectives, including the evaluation phase in the next coming weeks.

A total of 35 guidelines have been extracted for the acquisition, transmission, pre-processing, protection and storage stages of logging data for validation and evaluation, including detailed descriptions and examples from the PoDIUM project on how and why some guidelines have been applied. For the elicitation of the guidelines, the focus has been put on CCAM projects and, especially on European research projects like PoDIUM. These guidelines are a good baseline for engineering projects where data is key for the execution and evaluation phases.

Each of the PoDIUM use cases has described its data collection and storage implemented to extract the required metrics/logs to be able to validate the PoDIUM architecture and systems, as well as to address all KPIs for evaluation. The logging has been detailed enough to ease the replication in other systems and projects, being part of the guidelines in some sense as well. The storage details facilitate understanding the purpose of the data, since some will be disclosed in public repositories while others will be kept internally either temporarily or permanently due to privacy concerns and/or internal processing and analysis.

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References

- [1] Kern, M., Schulz, S., Wimmer, M., Buchholz, M. et al. **D3.2 “Initial report on the PoDIUM platform developments”**. PoDIUM project. Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069547. Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01. 2024.
- [2] Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. **The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship**. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016)
- [3] Dis, A., Zimmerman, W., Dirnwöber, M. et al. **D1.5 “Data Management Plan mid-term version”**. PoDIUM project. Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069547. Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01. 2024.
- [4] OpenAIRE. **“How to Comply with Horizon Europe Mandate for RDM”**. <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-with-horizon-europe-mandate-for-rdm>.
- [5] European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) and OpenAIRE. **“ZENODO”**. <https://zenodo.org/>.
- [6] European Union. (2016). Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (**General Data Protection Regulation**). Official Journal of the European Union, L119, 1-88.
- [7] CoreTrustSeal. <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>.
- [8] **C-Mobile project**. - H2020 | Project No. 723311. Call H2020-MG-2016-2017. 2016. <https://c-mobile-project.eu/>
- [9] **C-Roads**. <https://www.c-roads.eu/platform/about/about.html>.
- [10] Ulm University and Technischen Hochschule Ulm. **“OPARU: Open Access Repository of Ulm University and Ulm University of Applied Sciences”**. <https://oparu.uni-ulm.de/home>
- [11] **ZENODO PoDIUM project**. https://zenodo.org/communities/podium_project/about
- [12] Scheible, A., Visintainer, F., Vélez, G. et al. **“D5.1 PoDIUM evaluation methodology”**. PoDIUM project. Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069547. Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01. 2024.
- [13] **ETSI EN 302 637-2** Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Part 2: Specification of Cooperative Awareness Basic Service
- [14] **ETSI EN 302 637-3**; Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Part 3: Specifications of Decentralized Environmental Notification Basic Service
- [15] **ETSI TS 103 301**; Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Facilities layer protocols and communication requirements for infrastructure services; Release 2
- [16] **ETSI TS 103 324**; Intelligent Transport System (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Collective Perception Service; Release 2
- [17] **ETSI TS 103 300-3**; Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) awareness; Part 3: Specification of VRU awareness basic service; Release 2
- [18] nestor Certification Working Group. **nestor Seal for Trustworthy Digital Archives**. https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/EN/Zertifizierung/nestor_Siegel/siegel.html
- [19] International Organization for Standardization. (2012). **ISO 14721:2012** Space data and information transfer systems. 2012. <https://www.iso.org/standard/56510.html>